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Socio-Economic Influences and Reported Benefits of the implementation of Natural Water Retention Measures in the Morsa Catchment

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of Natural Water Retention Measures in the Morsa Catchment

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Summary

As climate change increases its impact on agriculture, strategies and solutions are developed to help mitigate its consequence on agriculture. Simultaneously, there is increasing pressure on agriculture to lessen its impact on the environment. Thus, there is a great need to find solutions that can benefit both agriculture and the environment. The OPTAIN project focuses on 14 catchments across 14 European countries and aims at finding practical and easily implementable water management practices that can help mitigate the impact of climate change on agriculture as well as the agricultural impact on the environment. As part of the ongoing OPTAIN project, this thesis looks into the socio-economic impacts on the implementation of natural water retention measures (NWRMs) in the Morsa catchment area (Norway) as well as their state of adoption, their reported benefits, and the observed impact of climate change on farms in the Morsa catchment area.

Through the distribution of an online questionnaire, 25 participants from the Morsa catchment were surveyed. An MFA was conducted to uncover correlations between various socio-economic factors and the implementation of NWRMs. In addition, basic analytical evaluation was conducted to report the current state of adoption of NWRMs, their reported benefits, as well the participant's observed impact of climate change on their farm.

This study finds that grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding, reduced tillage and buffer zones are the most employed measures by the farmers, with the highest observed benefits being reduction in soil loss, increased water quality, and protection against extreme weather events. Floods and especially droughts have been experienced by most participants during the last 10 years.

Regarding factors affecting the implementation of measures, this study finds education to have a direct, though quite weak, impact on the implementation of NWRMs. In addition, it finds that education, together with age and experience, have an indirect impact, through the influence of the participant's opinion on climate change and the practical benefits of measures. Furthermore, renting land seems to be a motivator in maintaining high water and soil quality. Grants and subsidies are also directly participating in the farmers implementation of measures. Finally, trust between the received source of information and the farmers also impact their will to implement NWRMs.

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1. Introduction

It is a well-known fact that water is of capital importance to all living creatures, from tiniest single celled organism to large mammals. To us human beings, water is used for our everyday necessities such as drinking, cooking, cleaning, but also for the production of electrical equipment, clothing, infrastructure, energy and agriculture. In addition, clean water is critical for sanitation, preventing the spread of diseases. Today, unfortunately, our industries have heavily impacted on our water quality, with many types of pollutants such as microplastics and chemicals (UN, n.d.). Notably, the agricultural sector is also participating in the decline of water quality through its use of agrochemicals and fertilizers, winding up in water bodies. This has become evident in the last decades on a global scale, with international organization such as the UN pushing towards solutions that help mitigate the impact of agriculture on the environment.

In addition to agriculture impacting water quality, agricultural production is also impacted by the effects of global warming. Extreme weather such as drought and heavy rainfall are increasingly recurrent and lead to soil degradation (I. Hanssen-Bauer & A.B. Sandø, 2016; Rust & Williams, n.d.).

Agriculture often thrives at the expense of water usage, water quality, biodiversity, and ecosystems. Three of the UNs Sustainable Development Goals attempt to push towards finding solutions to this problematic, notably “6 Clean water and sanitation”, “12 Responsible Consumption and Production” and “15 Life on Land” (Gulden, 2022). These goals are vital for global sustainability, public health, and environmental protection.

The European Union also contributes to these goals through policies as well as various funding programs, Horizon Europe being one of them. The Horizon Europe program focuses on funding research and innovation, as well as creating an environment that facilitates collaboration between research and innovation centers (European Commission, n.d.-b).

Finding solutions on a macro as well a micro level to help mitigate the effects of climate change is essential to maintaining the soil and water quality, as well minimizing the impact of agriculture on the environment.

1.1 OPTAIN

OPTAIN (OPTimal strategies to retAIN and re-use water and nutrients in small agricultural catchments) is a research and innovation project, funded through the Horizon Europe program, spanning from 2020 up until 2025 (OPTAIN, n.d.-a). Conflicting interest between actors as well as financial, technical and climate limitations are challenges that require an interdisciplinary and inclusive approach in order to find a balance as well as concrete solutions (Nemes, 2023). Through this approach, the OPTAIN project identifies efficient and practical natural water retention measures (NWRMs) and optimizes their spatial distribution and combination. The ambition is to enhance water management practices across various European ecological landscapes. The project focuses on 14 catchments across 14 European countries, split into 3 different biogeographical regions: boreal, continental and Pannonian (OPTAIN, n.d.-a). OPTAIN is driven by research centers across 15 European countries working closely with the stakeholders of each case study.

In order to reach its objective, OPTAIN has divided its plan into 9 work packages (WP), each having a specific objective in the overall project. This thesis contributes to WP 4: integrated assessment of NWRMs. WP 4 aims to quantitatively evaluate the effectiveness of NWRMs in the current and future climate of each case study. This evaluation will be conducted by combining both integrated process-based environmental modelling and conceptual socio-economic assessment at the field level and at the catchment scale across the 14 case studies (OPTAIN, n.d.-b). This thesis will focus on the Norwegian case study, which is part of the boreal biogeographical region.

1.2 The Norwegian case study

General description

A catchment area is an area of land in which water flows into a common drainage system such as a stream river, lake or other water body and is defined by the topography of the terrain (EEA, 2000). This study will focus on the Morsa catchment area, which is located in south south-eastern Norway and englobes the Vannsjø-Hobøl watercourse. Morsa spans from Drøbak in Frogn municipality in the north to Saltnes in Råde municipality in the south. It consists of 10 municipalities all located in the county of Viken (except for a small portion located in the county of Oslo). These municipalities are Enebakk, Frogn, Indre Østfold, Moss, Nordre Follo,

Oslo, Råde, Vestby, Våler and Ås. The Morsa catchment has a total land area of 1208 km² with around 100'000 inhabitants (Skarbøvik, 2021).

The county of Viken is by far the largest producers of cereals in Norway with almost 70% of its total crop production being cereal (NIBIO, 2023; SSB, 2023). This is due to the high quality of arable land, which is less prevalent in other areas of the country (NIBIO, 2023). Thus, farmers focus on crops, notably cereals, instead of livestock.

History

Designated by the ministry of the environment, and driven by the EU, Morsa catchment served as the pilot project for the practical implementation of the Water Framework Directive. Today, as the pilot project is complete, the catchment is subject to the same regulations that apply to other catchments in Norway (Morsa, n.d.). Agriculture and drainage are the main sources of eutrophication of the Vannsjø-Hobøl watercourse with a history of being polluted by nutrients, namely phosphorus, which also is the main lacking nutrient in Norwegian agriculture (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023d; Lyche Solheim et al., 2001).

1.3 Natural Water Retention Measures (NWRMs)

Natural water retention measures (NWRMs) are multi-functional nature-based solutions that help reduce impact of extreme weather conditions such as droughts and floods and simultaneously improve soil and water quality as well as improve biodiversity. They help contribute to climate change adaptation as well as mitigation (Hartmann et al., 2019; nwrn.eu, 2015). Intense precipitation on bare soil will create runoff, allowing soil nutrients to flow towards watercourses. This not only decreases soil quality from erosion, but also impacts water quality. Nutrients ending up in waterbodies, together with high temperatures creates ideal temperatures for the development of algae, making the water unusable to for example drinking (Skarbøvik et al., 2023). NWRMs are solutions that help reduce the impact of climate change on agriculture as well as the environment. The choice of the type of NWRMs will depend on the local needs.

Choice of NWRMs

In order to identify and select the NWRMs that would be studied in the Norwegian case study, a participatory workshop with stakeholders was organized. The stakeholders include farmers, landowners, representatives from local authorities and advisory experts. With the use of a questionnaire, the workshop identified and prioritized potential NWRMs based on their

perceived effectiveness in reducing sediment/soil particles load, phosphorus load, nitrogen load, and peak flow flattening (reducing impact of floods by slowing down rate at which water flows through a catchment). The workshop proposed NWRMs that were originally considered by OPTAINs case study leaders, as well as measures suggested by the workshop participants. The goal of this approach was to identify NWRMs that were both effective for the local needs and that were acceptable to farmers and landowners to maximize the chances of successful implementation of the NWRMs (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023f).

The 6 following measures were selected for the Norwegian case study:

- Grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding
- Grassed waterways
- Small constructed wetlands
- Reduced tillage
- Grass buffer zones
- Small retention pools in the forest

The Norwegian policy enables farmers to request grants for the implementation of certain measures, mainly through RMP- and SMIL-grants.

Grants for Special Environmental Measures in Agriculture (SMIL) are grants that can be requested for the implementation of measures that enhance the natural and cultural values of agricultural landscape and reduces pollution from agriculture (Landbruksdirektoratet, n.d.-b).

Grants from Regional Environment Program (RMP) be requested mainly within the context of reduction of pollution of water and air, preservation of natural landscapes and cultural heritage, outdoor recreation and conservation of biodiversity. Every county has its own environment program consisting of its own measures that can be subsidized by RMP. The measures are decided by the county governor and differ based on the local environmental challenges (Landbruksdirektoratet, n.d.-a).

1.3.1 Grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding

Figure 1: Flooded fields along the Hobøl river, Norway. Photo by Dominika Krzeminska

This measure implies using grass or stubble in arable land prone to flooding, meaning areas up to 22 meters from a watercourse that floods at least once every 10 years (Krzeminska, 2023).

The use of grass or stubble on arable land prone to flooding has shown to reduce soil erosion and nutrient loss due to runoff, improve soil surface porosity and hydraulic porosity which improves water infiltration. These improvements reduce the impact of floods. In addition, it can also improve soil quality and fertility (Huang et al., 2012).

The use of grass in areas prone to flooding can be supported by Norwegian policy in the form of subsidies as farmers use a portion of their arable land to grass instead of crops. Farmers can also receive subsidies for maintaining stubble across the field during the autumn season. It is a voluntary measure except if exposed watersheds are at risk of flooding in order to avoid pollution of for example drinking water (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023a)

1.3.2 Grassed waterways

Figure 2: Example of grassed waterway in Norway. Photo by Anne-Grete B. Blankenberg

Use of grassed waterways is described as the use of grass on natural waterflow pathways on the cropland. These pathways are naturally created by the topography of the terrain, which during heavy rainfall, are exposed to heavy erosion. (Lees et al., 2021). Thus, the main goal of using grass on waterways is to reduce the velocity of water runoff on the waterways, leading to a reduction of soil water erosion on these areas and improving water quality (Anomaa Senaviratne et al., 2013; Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023b). According to a study (Briggs et al., 1999), grassed waterways may reduce runoff volume by an average of 47% and herbicide residues by an average of 56%, making this a measure not only important to reduce erosion but also to limit the runoff of fertilizers and agrochemicals such as herbicides into the environment (Briggs et al., 1999). Furthermore, grassed waterways may be beneficial for the ecosystem providing habitat to the local fauna (Lees et al., 2021).

Grassed waterways are voluntary but supported by the Norwegian policy. Farmers can get subsidies from the County Governor (Statsforvalteren) to implement and maintain the measure. In addition they can receive advisory support from the Ministry of Agriculture and Food (LMD), the Norwegian Agriculture Advisory (NLR) and the Norwegian Research Institute of Bioeconomy (NIBIO) (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023b).

1.3.3 Small constructed wetlands

Figure 3: Example of small constructed wetland in Kråkstad catchment, Norway. Photo by Anne-Grete B. Blankenberg

Constructed wetlands are manmade areas built in order for water to cover or at least be near the soil surface all year round or during different periods of the year. These areas attract various types of plants and animals, both terrestrial and aquatic (EPA, 2023).

In agriculture, wetlands function by retaining and filtering agricultural runoff flowing from the cropland towards fresh- or saltwater bodies. The runoff gets filtered by organisms present in the wetland (HANSSON et al., 2005). Notably, plants such as reed grass (*Phragmites australis*) are commonly used for this process, also called phytoremediation (Volden, 2022)(process of cleaning soil, air or water with the use of plants (EPA, 2012)).

In Norway, one of the main sources of eutrophication in streams and lakes originate from phosphorus (P) and sediment runoff from agriculture. Thus, constructing wetlands enables to lessen the pollution in streams and lakes. Wetlands are generally designed to be composed of 3 different levels. The first one being the sedimentation pond, used to slow down and let particles settle. This pond is the deepest, while the two other ponds are more shallow and filled with vegetation used to filter and clean the water (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023d).

Farmers are able to request subsidies to implement and maintain wetlands through the County Governor (Statsforvalteren). In addition, they are able to receive advisory services from their municipality, the Ministry of Agriculture (LMD), the Norwegian Agricultural Advisory (NLR) and the Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO). Though greatly beneficial for environment by increasing biodiversity and improving water quality, the measure remains voluntary (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023d).

1.3.4 Reduced tillage

Figure 4: Field with stubble in Kråkstad catchment, Norway. Photo by Anne-Grete B. Blankenberg

Reduced tillage aims on minimizing soil disturbance by reducing tillage and by keeping stubble or plant cover during the autumn and winter season after harvesting (Skaalsveen, 2023).

This reduces soil erosion and loss of soil particles and nutrients into watercourses, which results in improved water quality in the watercourses. In addition, reducing tillage also increases

organic matter content on the cropland which in turn might increase the aggregate stability of the upper layers of the soil (Skaalsveen, 2023). Reduced tillage improves soil structure and can reduce compaction due to the concentration of decomposing crop residues as well as an increase in earthworms. However, on the long run it could increase compaction due to sustained physical degradation resulting from long-term topsoil and subsoil compaction (Peigné et al., 2007). In turn, reducing tillage will also affect the farmers economy by reducing labor demand and fuel consumption. The decrease in production costs will depend on the specific tillage system and crop rotation (Peigné et al., 2007).

Subsidies are available based on the level of erosion risk. This measure is voluntary, though in exposed watersheds, it is mandatory for farmers to implement stricter management practices including reduced tillage on at least 60% of the area in order to prevent soil erosion. The Directorate Group for Implementation of Water Regulation gives guidelines on the implementation of reduced tillage and subsidies are given by the Norwegian Environment Agency (Miljødirektoratet) and the County Governor (Statsforvalteren) (Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023c).

1.3.5 Grass buffer zones

Figure 5: Buffer zone along the Hobøl River, Norway. Photo by Dominika Krzeminska

Grass buffer zones are strips of grass situated on the downslope of cropland, prior to a stream bank. This enables a cheap way (both implementation and maintenance) to reduce runoff of nutrients, sediments and agrochemicals through filtration, deposition, and infiltration (Dillaha et al., 1989; Zhang et al., 2010). In addition, buffer zones may also enhance biodiversity by creating a habitat for insect, birds and animals (Krzeminska et al., 2023).

Depending on the region in Norway, buffer zones along stream and lakes are mandatory or voluntary. In Morsa, implementing buffer zones is mandatory along streams and lakes. Farmers receive subsidies to implement and maintain a buffer zone by the County Governor (Statsforvalteren) and the municipality. In addition, farmers may receive production subsidies, meaning compensation for the loss of cropland. However, if the buffer zone is not maintained as required by the law, subsidies may be removed (Krzeminska et al., 2023).

1.3.6 Small retention pools in the forest

Figure 6: Example of small retention pool in Våler, Norway. Photo by Dominika Krzeminska

Small retention pools are small dams or reservoirs that slow down water flow generally made from soil, stone and or with gabions (Hartmann et al., 2019; Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023e). They are located in the forest and generally contain little to no water during dry periods but retain water during rainfall events. This measure helps mitigate the impact of floods (Krzeminska, 2022).

Small retention pools in the forest are a voluntary measure and is not very common yet. Nonetheless the measure is supported by the Norwegian policy and farmers can receive subsidies to implement this measure (Krzeminska, 2022; Krzeminska & Blankenberg, 2023e).

1.4 Objectives of thesis

This thesis is a survey-based study that will try to determine the current state of implementation and knowledge of NWRMs as well as the challenges faced, and attitudes farmers have towards adaption to climate change. Finally, we will try to find correlations between the adoption of NWRMs and the various local socio-economic factors.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Survey Adaptation and Customization

Adapting the OPTAIN questionnaire to the Norwegian context

Originally, the OPTAIN project's questionnaire was designed for a large audience across 14 EU countries. This wide scope led to a version that turned out to be too general for the Norwegian agricultural context. In order to increase our chances of getting responses from the farmers we had to revise the questionnaire substantially in order to make it fit better with Norway's specific farming practices and conditions, as well as its system of environmental and farmer organization. Input from researchers at NIBIO was crucial for this step. This helped to get a better understanding of the role of various organizations that are in contact with the farmers, as well as the function of the various measures and enabled the use of precise terminology in the survey. The knowledge and experience of the senior researchers at the NIBIO institute enabled a pertinent adaptation of the survey to not only the Norwegian context but specifically to the Morsa catchment area as well. This was done through shared documentation such as PowerPoint presentations regarding the measures, guidance such as language adjustments, information regarding the various agricultural advisors and added relevant questions to the survey.

Transition to online survey

The original survey was made for in-person interviews with the farmers. Personal interviews would limit the number of participants in the study, in addition to using around 1 hour to fill in the survey. Furthermore, there would also have been logistical disadvantages such as organizing meetings that suits each individual, organizing travel for the research team if the meeting were to take place at the responder's place, or organizing a meeting space if the survey was done at the research center. Therefore, in order to ease the data collection process and to maximize response rates by reaching out to more people, we chose to create an online version of the survey.

Although shifting from an in-person type survey to an online survey has many advantages, there are also some associated risks. For example, not everybody in society may feel comfortable with the use of computers. Also, some may feel insecure about answering online surveys due to fear of data breaches or fraud. These group may therefore be underrepresented. According to national statistics, the average age of Norwegian farmers was 52.2 years at the time of the latest survey in 2020 (Lasse Eika, 2022). Naturally, there is variation in their age, but at this average age we can assume both sufficient degree of computer literacy, and sufficient degree of awareness of internet-security. These two traits combined made me conclude that the transition to an online platform will not pose substantial limits to the number of responses, but

perhaps may even increase it overall. There may, however, be some issues with clarity in an online survey. While the questions seemed clear to us, some questions might be unclear to some farmers. This could give us some incorrect data which might be avoided in an interview where responders can ask for help if some questions seem unclear to them. Additionally, while filling a survey online, the responder could get impatient and give less accurate responses to complete the survey more rapidly. This might be less of an issue in an interview. Furthermore, when conducting an online survey there is a risk that the number of responses received are far fewer than desired. An in-person interview will secure the number of responders desired, though will limit the possible amount of responders at the same time, especially in a time constrained scenario as in our case.

Finding and choosing the right online survey program is a crucial step as it may impact the overall success of the survey. One very important goal for the choice of the survey program was to maximize response rates. In order to select the most suitable online survey platform, we evaluated a number of platforms using a multi-criteria system that accounted for its complexity, aesthetics, flow, instinctiveness, and the choice of its available tools for the development of the survey. In addition, the choice was also based on the amount of available content in the free version of the program, as this would enable to explore the platform and understand its functions before engaging in a subscription. Finally, it is also important to note that some subscriptions are yearly whereas others are monthly, largely affecting the subscription price as the program would only be used for at most 2 months.

It was also important to find a program from which data could easily be exported to other software's to be analyzed. Finally, having many functions available in the program in order to build up the survey would broaden the user's options and therefore lessen the limitations posed by the platform.

Long questionnaires may reduce respondent willingness, and if we do not consider this factor and introduce measures to avoid it, surveys may trigger stakeholder fatigue in frequently surveyed areas. The original OPTAIN survey was composed mostly of tables, with multiple options to choose from in each cell. In most cells, the option "Other" was available, with the possibility of writing what the "Other" answer was using free text. This made it difficult to transition from a classic table format in a word processor file to an online survey table since choosing multiple answers and adding a free-text box when selecting a specific answer can rarely, if ever, be combined and implemented.

One possibility that can help solve the issue is if the tables are converted into a series of multiple-choice questions, with an “other” option at the end of the options that would spawn a text box if selected. Combining multiple-choice questions with conditional logic enables to translate the tables into a series of questions that can be adapted to each responder, increasing the efficiency of the questionnaire. Therefore, when searching for the appropriate survey platform, it was key that the platform support conditional logic. The outcome of the selection process and the justification for selecting the JotForm platform is presented in the Results section. However, understanding the platform is important for the next steps, hence it is introduced below.

JotForm

JotForm survey platform was selected for its user-friendly interface and simple experience for both the development of the questionnaire and for the completion of the survey by the participants. The program is instinctive, which enabled a rapid learning curve. In addition, *JotForm* has the options to insert “widgets” which expands the possibilities in creating a well-tailored survey. Widgets are extensions, often created by individuals that are external to *JotForm*. This enables individuals to develop an extension that can help solve a demand that they encountered or that they know exist, diversifying the overall available functions on the platform. Since Sikt (see Sikt - Compliance with Regulatory Requirements) required signatures from the participants proving that they agreed on participating, the “Signature” widget was implemented, enabling participants to easily sign the survey directly on the platform. Additionally, *JotForm* allowed easy learning and experimentation with its functionalities under the “free trial” period before purchasing its fully functional license.

2.2 Sikt - Compliance with Regulatory Requirements

Before being able to distribute the survey, approval from Sikt was required by the Norwegian University of Life Sciences. Sikt is the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research, which works under the Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research and provides services such as information security and data protection. The agency ensures that the research adheres to the legal and ethical requirement for studies that involve human subjects in Norway. Notably through the General Data Protection Regulations art.6 nr 1a and art.9 nr 2a that ensures that all participants consent to the use of personal data (personopplysningsloven, 2016; Sikt, n.d.).

Two requests were sent to Sikt. Firstly, the original OPTAIN survey was sent to Sikt at the very start of the development of the final survey, hoping this would be approved and would not need to be concerned about compliance with regulatory requirements any further. As this version received some criticism, we had to send our second request with the final version of the survey. Extensive changes were made to reach the final version of the survey. The changes made to comply with the Sikt regulations did not confront our own goals, but rather aligned with our goals to simplify and adapt the survey to the Norwegian context. The second request was finally approved before the distribution of the survey.

2.3 Distribution of the Survey

Maximizing our surveys response rate through its distribution was an important step. To do this we chose to present the survey online and collaborated with 2 municipality's agricultural office (Våler og Indre Østfold Landbrukskontor), as well as the Ski og Kråkstad farmer union (Bondelag). We requested to distribute the survey among active farmers under their respective jurisdiction/membership. This collaboration with the agricultural offices as well as the farmers union has likely contributed to an enhanced response rate.

In total, approximately 250 farmers received the survey: 74 people in Indre Østfold, 90 in Våler and 87 from the Ski og Kråkstad Bondelag. It is important to note that not everyone in the Ski og Kråkstad Bondelag are part of the MORSA catchment area and therefore were not involved in the survey.

2.4 Analysis of Survey Responses

After importing all the answers from the participants in an *excel-file*, a need for data preprocessing was required. Questions with multiple possible answers had to be separated in several columns, corresponding to the number of possible answers. This had to be implemented as all the selected answers from a single question by an individual were all listed in a single cell, causing improper data-processing during the data analysis. Departing from 117 columns in the *excel-file*, each corresponding to a single question, the number of columns after this phase of the data preprocessing was multiplied to 254 columns.

After analyzing and illustrating general information from the data with the use of excel, the use of multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) as well as multiple factor analysis (MFA) was employed. This was done through *R* with the *Factoshiny* package (Husson et al., 2023) in order

to compare the relationship between variables, such as age, experience, implementation of measure, education etc.. This step enabled a more pertinent and simplified correlation analysis between the variables. Using a single *.csv-file* with all the data and attempting an MFA caused an override of data, making information unreadable. For this reason, three separate *csv-files* were created. A selection of variables was made for each *.csv-file* based on the relevancy and interest of a comparison with one another.

In order to find the correlation between socio-economic variables and the implementation of the measures, a *.csv-file* was built with the following variables:

- Age (numerical)
- Years as farmer (numerical)
- Implementation of the measure (binary)
- Household size (numerical)
- Municipality (qualitative)
- Education (Qualitative)
- Income (numerical)
- Whether farming is the main income or not (binary)
- Land area owned (numerical)
- Land area rented (numerical)

A second *.csv-file* was made to find the correlation between the opinions of the participants on a series of statements with socio-economic factors as well as their decision on the implementation of the measures. This file contained the following variables:

- Opinions on statements (qualitative)
- Age and experience (numerical)
- Household size (numerical)
- Income (numerical)
- Whether farming is main income or not (binary)
- Implementation of the measures (binary)
- Education (qualitative)

Age and experience were merged in as a same variable since during initial MFA analysis it was found that they had a very high correlation between one another.

Finally, to find the impact of different organizations such as NLR (Norsk Landbruksrådgivning), Bondelag, NIBIO etc. as well as grant sources such as SMIL or RMP (Regional Miljøplan) and the implementation of the measures as well as the participant's scale of knowledge on the measures, a third *.csv-file* was made, including the following variables:

- Implementation of the measures (binary)
- Scale of knowledge of the measures (scale from 1-5)
- Full and/or partial grants from RMP and/or SMIL (qualitative)
- Whether they received information on the measure (binary)
- Whether they received information on the measures from any of the 5 organizations (NIBIO, NLR, Bondelag, Morsa, PURA, Agricultural office) (binary)
- Age (numerical)

An organization of the data in excel, along with titles, allowed for a dataset that could be examined with more ease and less confusion. This facilitated the creation of basic excel graphs to show the number of participants having selected a certain answer. In addition, the questions were modified in order to change the possible selected answers to a binary dataset, Yes/No, which would further facilitate data analysis. Another pertinent modification was the correction of data. The use of conditional logic in the survey made some questions unavailable to some participants. This resulted in having to correct some data. For example, participants were asked to select the measures they knew out of the 6 proposed measures. Participants having not selected a certain measure were not confronted with follow-up questions regarding the measure such as the scale of knowledge of the measure, or whether they implement the measure or not. Following a logic conclusion, the data was modified so that participants having not chosen a certain measure, were given a 1 out of 5 on the scale of knowledge of the measure, as well as a “No” on whether the measure was implemented or not. This enabled to always use all 25 participants during the analysis. Additionally, some modifications regarding answers selected by participants were made as well. For example, one participant reported not using any measure to counter droughts, whilst at the same time selecting a measure to counter droughts. The selection of “no measure used” was therefore removed as the participant later reported having used a measure. Finally, two participants specified their education using a “text box” that appeared in the survey when selecting the “Other” option. These were included as such in the first phase of the analysis, with excel, but were changed during the MFA/MCA analysis, replacing their specification with the study fields that were originally proposed, using the number of years of the study as a reference to categorize them in the right educational level. Several changes similar to the ones described were implemented in order to have a corrected dataset. Some data was ignored during the analysis as there were too little variations that wouldn’t impact or that would negatively impact the analysis. Information such as gender of the participants or the position in the farm, was ignored since only 1 participant was a woman and 2 participants were non-farm-owners. Thus, no statistical information could be extracted from this information.

Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) is a merging of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for quantitative variables, Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) for qualitative variables, and Correspondence Analysis (CA) for frequency variables. MFAs allow multiple sets of variables to be analyzed simultaneously which allows the visualization of the relationship between different types of variables (qualitative, quantitative and frequency). Resulting from the

analysis are graphs as well as tables indicating the correlation between variables, groups of variables, or individuals (XLSTAT, n.d.-a).

While analyzing with the use of MFAs, it was noticed that the graphs created from the data could easily be misinterpreted. Therefore, it was decided to use tables including RV coefficients instead unless there was certainty in the data showed in the graphs. The RV coefficient is derived from the log coefficient, which measures the number of similar variables in two sets of data. The RV coefficient is represented by a number between 0 to 1, with 1 meaning the two sets of data are identical, and 0 meaning they have no correlation. The RV coefficient is a generalization of the squared Pearson correlation coefficient, made to include multiple dimensions (XLSTAT, n.d.-a; XLSTAT, n.d.-b).

3. Results

3.1 Choosing the online survey platform

In order to select the right program, a comparison was made between 5 programs:

- *Survey Xact*
- *SurveyMonkey*
- *Qualtrics*
- *JotForm*
- *GoogleForms*

In order to better compare the different platforms, a table was implemented comparing on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being lowest grade and 5 the highest, factors such as aesthetics, simplicity, instinctiveness, flow, choice of tools (widgets), conditional logic and the amount of content in the free version. Additionally, we included whether the program had possibilities to create complex tables (as described on p. 13) and whether the program had the option of having monthly subscriptions instead of yearly.

Only *JotForm* survey platform has been thoroughly explored compared to the other programs listed. Since not all the functions have been fully tested across the list of programs, this comparison is a conclusion of personal experience during the testing of the programs.

Table 1: Table showing the grading of the 5 online platforms from 1 to 5, with 1 being the lowest and 5 the highest grade. Empty cells are present when the features have not been tested or observed.

	<i>Survey Xact</i>	<i>SurveyMonkey</i>	<i>Qualtrics</i>	<i>GoogleForms</i>	<i>JotForm</i>
Aesthetics	1	4	5	2	4
Simplicity	1	3	3	3	5
Instinctiveness	1	2	4	3	5
Flow		4	5	2	5
Choice of tools		3	3	1	5
Conditional logic		3	5	3	3
Complex tables	No	No	No	No	No
Available content in free version		3	4	5	5
Yearly / Monthly subscription		Yearly	Yearly	Free	Monthly/Yearly

In general terms, for the creation of the survey, *JotForm* scored highest in many areas which explains the choice for its usage for the creation of the online survey. Nonetheless, *Qualtrics* was graded quite highly on many important points, notably for conditional logic.

The first criteria that was researched for the selection of the online platform was the possibility of the creation of complex tables. The complex tables sought were tables having the possibility of including free text when the “Other” option was selected in a cell, as well as having the possibility of selecting multiple answers in a same cell. Unfortunately, having tested all 5 platforms, none of them possessed this feature.

Most survey platforms seemed to only have yearly subscriptions available. In some cases, such as in *SurveyMonkey*, there are monthly subscriptions available, but with limited content compared to the yearly subscriptions, which are more expensive. The subscription plans offered in *JotForm* seemed to have less limitations compared to some other platforms.

The vast choice of tools was also an important factor that proved to be critical in the simplification of the survey. The use of widgets, namely the “Signature” widget helped simplify the process of the signature for the participants. Since Sikt required signatures from the participants proving that they agreed on participating, the widget enabled participants to easily sign the survey directly in app. Additionally, *JotForm* allowed to use all of its functionalities for free before having to buy the program in order to add more questions. This allowed to understand the program before buying a subscription. On the other hand, other platforms required to pay for the subscription in order to be able to use some basic functionalities.

3.2 Outcome of the Compliance Assessment by Sikt

An early request for approval with the original survey version was sent to Sikt. Knowing we would translate and potentially remove and add some questions, Sikt requested the final form in order to approve our request. In addition, this version received criticism concerning the collection of personal data. The original survey included questions regarding decision making in the household, notably regarding income management. While we found those questions to lack relevance in Norway and to be borderline intrusive, these questions were straight-out denied by Sikt under the General Data Protection Regulations art.6 nr 1a and art.9 nr 2a, which requires consent from each individual if the responder is to answer questions regarding the household participation of, for example, economic management. In addition, Sikt requested that we include an information letter, detailing how the personal data of the responders will be collected and stored as well as asking them for their consent through a signature. The type of personal data that would be collected and stored was also detailed.

The changes request by Sikt for reasons of compliance, while they helped better adapt the survey to the Norwegian context and contributed to its simplification.

Upon finalizing the survey, Sikt was contacted again for their approval, which was granted. In this version we removed questions regarding other household members, included a cover letter, and facilitated collecting the responders’ signature directly in the survey app. The latter feature made the participation in the survey simpler by removing the necessity/complexity to send extra documentation to each participant and collecting their signature in an external word/PDF document., which in turn, could have dissuaded some respondents to participate.

3.3 How the original and final surveys compare

Although the original objective was to simplify and translate the original OPTAIN survey, a lot more had to be changed. These modifications were critical to reduce confusion, avoid questions that the farmer might consider intrusive, as well as remove any questions irrelevant in the Norwegian context. This enabled a well-adapted and much simpler and shorter questionnaire for the responders. In addition, the questionnaire was converted from an in-person survey to an online one. Furthermore, although the platform was chosen for its simplicity, the platform was new to this user and therefore a substantial portion of time was also used to learn the functionalities and limits of *JotForm* to maximize the potential from the chosen online platform. In total, approximately 1 month was used to complete the final survey from the original OPTAIN survey.

The survey was sent to around 250 individuals, though not every person was part of the Morsa catchment. Kråkstad and Ski Bondelag have farmers working throughout the Morsa catchment but also the PURA catchment, just north of Morsa. Therefore, it is not known how many of the 250 people were not part of the Morsa catchment but we assume the number doesn't significantly deviate from 250. The survey was available for the responders during a 13-day period. At the end of this period, a total of 25 responses were collected. This results in a 10% response rate. 15 out of 25 responses were collected during the first 2 days of the survey being distributed.

The average completion time of the survey was 22:30 minutes with the average responder answering approximately 107 questions, depending on the pattern of selected answers. This gives an average completion time of 12 seconds per question.

3.4 Analysis of key driving factors

The results from the survey show that 24 men and 1 woman responded to the survey, with 17 participants being from Våler, 6 from Indre Østfold and 2 from Nordre Follo municipality.

22 participants are either farm owners or co-owners whilst one participant is a farm manager, one is an employee and one decided not to respond to this question. Nearly all participants are married or live with their partner with only one participant being divorced and one not giving out the civil status.

3.4.1 Implementation of water retention measures

For each measure known by the participants, they were asked where they had heard about it. In Figure 7 we combined the answers of all the participants and for all the measures. We can observe that RMP and/or SMIL-grants play a large role on the distribution of information on the various water retention measures.

We also observe a high percentage of information received from guidance as well as from personal knowledge and expertise.

Figure 7: Column chart showing where participants heard about the 6 NWRMs. Participants could choose multiple answers.

In addition to the source of information for each measure, participants were asked whether they implemented the measure or not, if they were planning to, or if they previously had the measure in place but decided to abandon it. Responders who reported having used the measure in the past and participants having the measure in place were also asked to report on the observed benefits of the measure, while participants who decided not to implement and participants who had the measure in place in the past, were asked the reasons for not implementing or abandoning it. It is important to note that only participants who have selected the measure as a “known” measure could respond to this question. Therefore, responders who aren’t informed

on the measure are excluded from reporting on the reasons for not implementing the measure. These results are shown below, categorized by each individual measure.

Grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding

Figure 8: Pie chart showing the number of participants that use grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding.

80% of participants implemented grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding as represented in Figure 8, with a small percentage of those having put in place the measure saying that no benefits were observed (Figure 9), including the one responder that used to have the measure in place but no longer has. As participants could write a comment for each measure, almost a third of the participants shared their opinions with a large portion describing this measure as having only benefits. Notably the reduction of topsoil erosion. One participant also acknowledged having been obliged by the county governor to implement this measure two decades ago, but now observes a lot of positive results.

Figure 9: Column chart showing the benefits of the use of grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding. Each participant could choose multiple benefits.

The two participants that do not have the measure in place or stopped implementing it (Figure 8), say that the reason for not implementing the measure is the absence of need. In addition, the participant that used to have grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding also stated that there was a low benefit to cost ratio as well too low subsidies as reasons for abandoning this measure.

Grassed waterways

The use of grass on waterways is applied by 32% of the participants as shown in Figure 10. though a couple of participants are planning to implement the measure in the future.

Figure 10: Pie chart showing the number of responders having implemented grassed waterways on their farm.

54% of participants having applied grass on waterways observed reduced of soil erosion and soil loss. In addition, 37,5% stated that the implementation of this measure has helped them counter extreme weather events (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Column chart showing the benefits of the use of grassed waterways. Participants could select multiple answers. Only participants that implemented the measure were able to describe the benefits.

As for the reasons for not implementing grassed waterways, most participants report not having the need for it, as well as a couple of participants reporting a high maintenance or administration cost (Figure 12). In addition, 2 participants reported the abandoning of the usage of grassed waterways as being a result of the cessation of the renting of a field.

Figure 12: Column chart showing the reasons reported by the participants having not implemented grassed waterways, or having had the measure in the past, but not currently.

Small constructed wetlands

Figure 13: Pie chart showing the number of participants having implemented small constructed wetlands on their farm.

Small constructed wetlands are implemented by 40% of the participants (Figure 13) with most participants mentioning soil particle retention as an observed benefit as well as nutrient retention in addition to the usage of sediments after emptying the wetland (Figure 14). 2 participants not having constructed small wetlands report the lack of need for this measure with one participant describing having straightened the river with the use of stone as the reason for not needing to construct a wetland, mentioning that it had far greater effect for water quality than wetlands.

Figure 14: Column chart showing the benefits of the presence of a small constructed wetland. Only participants that implemented the measure were able to indicate the benefits of the use of this measure (10 responders).

Reduced tillage

Figure 15: Pie chart showing the number of participants reducing tillage on their farm.

As illustrated in Figure 15, only 4 participants out of 25 do not implement reduced tillage. Both participants having answered “No” have livestock as their main production. Reduced soil erosion and soil loss are both reported by the majority of the responders as being an observed benefit from the reduction of tillage (Figure 16). It is also noted by almost half of the participants that a water quality increase was observed. One participant having livestock as its main production, has reported the lack of need as a reason for not implementing the measure. In addition, 2 participants mentioned high investment as a reason for not reducing tillage and one of them added lack of training or equipment as another reason.

Figure 16: Column chart showing the observed benefits of reduced tillage. Only participants implementing this measure as well as participants that used to implement it were able to respond.

Grass buffer zones

Figure 17: Pie chart showing the number of participants using buffer zones as a water retention measure.

Almost 70 % of participants use buffer zones as a water retention measure (Figure 17), and most of them have reported reduced soil erosion and soil loss and increased water quality as observed benefits (Figure 18). Almost half of the participants having implemented the measure also reported that implementing buffer zones helped them counter extreme weather conditions.

Figure 18: Column chart showing the reported benefits of the use of buffer zones by the participants. Each participant had the option of reporting multiple benefits. Only participants who have the measure in place were able to respond.

Three participants having not implemented buffer zones as a measure reported no need as their reason. One of them further reported high investment, high maintenance or administration

costs, not enough subsidies, bad cost to benefit ratio as well as technical complications for the implementation as being reasons for not having the measure in place.

Small retention pools in the forest

Figure 19: Pie chart showing the number of participants having implemented small retention pools in the forest.

In contrast to other measures, the use of small retention pools in the forest is implemented by a minority of the responders as shown in Figure 19. Most of these 5 participants reported reduced flood risk, reduced soil erosion and soil loss on the field below as well as a good counter to extreme weather as being observed benefits from the use of this measure.

Figure 20: Column chart showing the benefits of the use of small retention pools in the forest. Only the 5 participants that have implemented the measure were able to give their feedback. Each participant was able to report multiple benefits.

3 Participants having not implemented this measure stated that the reasons for not carrying out this measure were technical barriers, lack of training or equipment, high investments and not enough subsidies.

3.4.2 Extreme weather events

We asked participants to indicate extreme weather conditions that have been observed on their farm the last 10 years, from 2013 to 2023 (Figure 21). All 25 participants reported experiencing droughts and 72% reported experiencing floods or excess water. 4 participants also reported experiencing other extreme weather events such as hailstorms, strong winds or late frost.

Figure 21: Column chart showing the number of participants having experienced extreme weather events on their farm the last 10 years (2013-2023).

Droughts

Figure 22: Column chart showing the number of responders who have observed droughts regularly or occasionally.

Figure 22 shows that 72% of the responders have observed droughts occasionally on their farm the last 10 years, whereas the remaining 28% have observed droughts regularly. What is important to note is that classifying “occasionally” and “regularly” will not only depend on the number of observed droughts by the responder but will also depend on what the responder classifies as “occasionally” or “regularly”. As we have also asked responders to count the number of droughts observed the last 10 years, we can see that “occasional” and “regular” will sometimes not depend on the number of times observed but rather on personal perception. This is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 24: Bar chart showing the different measures used by the participants to counter droughts.

9 participants out of 25 did not implement any measure to counter droughts. On the other hand, one third of participants that did try to counter droughts reported using crop rotation or mixing several crops. One third also reported the use of insurance schemes for the crops. In addition, one quarter of the participants had to postpone the date of sowing or of harvesting.

Floods and water excess

18 out of 25 participants noted observing floods or excess water on their farm during the last 10 years with all but one participant observing the last flood or excess water in 2023. With half of them reporting observing it regularly and the other half occasionally. Just as for droughts, the variation in the perception of what is regular and occasional is also seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Column chart showing whether responders believe floods or excess water have been regular or occasional on their farm the last 10 years compared to the number of observed floods or excess water on their farm the last 10 years.

Almost 90% of participants stated using grass in areas prone to flooding as well as improving their hydrotechnical facilities as a countermeasure. 70% also reported increasing protection of streams or rivers to limit erosion.

Figure 26: Bar chart showing the different measures employed by the participants to counter floods and excess water.

3.4.3 Socio-economic factors

Participants of the survey were asked to select their educational level. As shown in Figure 27, 32% of participants have a master's degree, 24% have a bachelor's degree and 28% of participants did not pursue further studies after high school. As participants had the option to write an answer if none of the options available corresponded to them, we received one participant describing their background in forestry and agricultural school, as well as another with a background in professor studies. In addition, one participant did not finish the bachelor studies, and another chose not to respond to this question.

Figure 27: Pie chart showing education level of participants. 1 participant did not give this information.

Figure 28: Column chart representing the average amount of measures known by the participants, with each column representing their educational background. The number next to the education represents the number of participants. The Y-axis represents the average number of measures known.

The responders were asked to select the measures that are known to them from the 6 water retention measures. By comparing the number of known measures together with education, we can observe in Figure 28 that people's knowledge on water retention measures seem to be affected by their education level. Participants with a master's degree score higher than participants with a bachelor's degree, and participants that did not pursue further studies after high school score lower than the other two. Although the participant with forestry and agricultural school background and the participant with professor studies background scored highest and lowest respectively, these values have low statistical significance since they each

only each represent one participant. The same can be said for the participant who did not complete the bachelor studies.

Using an MFA, we found whether there was any correlation between education and the implementation of the measures by comparing the implementation of each measure and education. This would additionally enable to see whether there is a correlation between the implementation of two measures.

	Edu	G.S	GW	SCW	RT	BZ	SRP	MFA
Edu	1.00	0.17	0.03	0.11	0.16	0.04	0.04	0.65
G.S	0.17	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.40
GW	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.29	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.42
SCW	0.11	0.00	0.29	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.10	0.47
RT	0.16	0.04	0.09	0.04	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.42
BZ	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.02	0.33
SRP	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.10	0.05	0.02	1.00	0.37
MFA	0.65	0.40	0.42	0.47	0.42	0.33	0.37	1.00

Legend:

G.S = Grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding

GW = Grassed waterways

Edu = Education level

SCW = Small Constructed Wetlands

RT = Reduced tillage

BZ = Buffer zones

SRP = Small retention pools in the forest

Table 2: RV coefficients showing the relationship between the implementation of each measure and the educational level.

In the figure above we see the correlation between the various variables. An RV coefficient of 1 means that both variables are identical and an RV coefficient of 0 means that there is strictly no correlation between the two variables. Thus, the higher the coefficient, the more correlated they are. In Table 2 we see that there is a small but still present correlation between education and the implementation of Grass or stubble (G.S) (RV = 0.17), reduced tillage (RT) (RV = 0.16), as well as for small constructed wetlands (SCW) (R = 0.11) to a lesser degree. These coefficients however are quite small and therefore not very significant. Nonetheless, when comparing the implementation of the measures to one another, we find a moderate correlation

between the implementation of grassed waterways and small constructed wetlands, whereas the other measures have close to no correlation at all with one another.

Opinions on the environment

A series of statements were given to the participants. The statements were divided into 3 categories. In the first category (Q1) participants had to state their agreeableness with the statements. In the second category (Q2), participants had to give the importance of the statements. The third and last category (Q3) were statements about the future of agriculture where again, participants had to give their agreeableness with the statements.

For the first category, participants were led to express their agreeableness on 3 statements related to small constructed wetlands and buffer zones. They could either strongly disagree, disagree, be neutral, agree or strongly agree.

Figure 29: Pie charts showing the agreeableness of participants on the Q1 statements.

We can see a general agreeableness of just above 50% for the Q1 statements with participants agreeing or strongly agreeing. There is however also a good portion of uncertainty as well as a slight portion of disagreeableness regarding the practical benefits of buffer zones and small constructed wetlands.

Using an MFA, a measure of the relationship between socio-economic factors and the responses given by the participants to the Q1 statements was made (Table 3). In addition, we can observe the correlation between these opinions and the implementation of the combined measures.

	AgeEXP	Fam	Inc	Edu	FisM	Impl	Q1	MFA
AgeEXP	1.00	0.37	0.01	0.04	0.18	0.06	0.26	0.47
Fam	0.37	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.13	0.40
Inc	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.09	0.17	0.31
Edu	0.04	0.05	0.00	1.00	0.04	0.20	0.30	0.58
FisM	0.18	0.08	0.01	0.04	1.00	0.07	0.08	0.33
Impl	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.20	0.07	1.00	0.25	0.54
Q1	0.26	0.13	0.17	0.30	0.08	0.25	1.00	0.74
MFA	0.47	0.40	0.31	0.58	0.33	0.54	0.74	1.00

Legend:

AgeEXP = Age and Experience

Edu = Education level

Q1 = Q1 statements

Fam = Household size

FisM = Farmins is main income

Inc = Income

Impl = Implementation of measure

Table 3: *RV coefficients showing the relationship between various socio-economic factors, the implementation of the measures and the opinions of the participants on the Q1 statements.*

We can observe a somewhat moderate correlation between the opinions of the Q1 statements and education ($RV = 0.30$), as well as a somewhat moderate correlation with age and experience ($RV = 0.26$) as well as with the implementation of all the measures ($RV = 0.25$). Additionally, there is a weak correlation between the Q1 statements and income ($RV = 0.17$) and household size ($RV = 0.13$) and almost no correlation with farming being the main income ($RV = 0.08$).

The second category of question asks the farmers about the importance given to statements about the environment and the availability of information and support. The possible answers that the participants could choose for the Q2 statements were: Very unimportant, unimportant, unsure, important, very important.

Figure 30: Pie charts showing the level of importance given by the participants to the Q2 statements.

Most responders either believe the statements shown in Figure 30 are important or very important, with a small portion of responders not being certain in some cases.

We can observe the relationship between the opinions on the Q2 statements and the socio-economic factors, as well as the relationship between these opinions and the implementation of the combined measures.

	AgeEXP	Fam	Inc	Edu	FisM	Impl	Q2	MFA
AgeEXP	1.00	0.37	0.01	0.04	0.18	0.06	0.11	0.46
Fam	0.37	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.14	0.45
Inc	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.09	0.08	0.31
Edu	0.04	0.05	0.00	1.00	0.04	0.20	0.12	0.57
FisM	0.18	0.08	0.01	0.04	1.00	0.07	0.09	0.38
Impl	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.20	0.07	1.00	0.22	0.58
Q2	0.11	0.14	0.08	0.12	0.09	0.22	1.00	0.53
MFA	0.46	0.45	0.31	0.57	0.38	0.58	0.53	1.00

Legend:

AgeEXP = Age and Experience

Edu = Education level

Q2 = Q2 statements

Fam = Household size

FisM = Farmins is main income

Inc = Income

Impl = Implementation of measure

Table 4: RV coefficients showing the relationship between various socio-economic factors, the implementation of the measures and the opinions of the participants on the Q2 statements.

We can notice in Table 4 a somewhat moderate relationship between the opinions of the Q2 statements and the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.22). In addition, there seems to be a slight, although weak, correlation between household size (RV = 0.14), education (RV = 0.12) and age and experience (RV = 0.11) and the opinions of these statements.

The third category of questions asks the participants about the importance they give to the Q3 statements, which are descriptions of the possible future of agriculture. Participants could either strongly disagree, disagree, be neutral, agree or strongly agree. Blanks left by the participant were categorized as “unsure”.

Q.3.1: In the future there will be more intense and frequent extreme weather events that affect the availability and usability of water (water shortage and/or surplus)

Q.3.2: In the future there will be increased conflicts between end users over natural resources (ie land and water)

Q.3.3: In the future agricultural policy will address additional environmental obligations.

Q.3.4: In the future there will be unfavorable production costs and market prices for crops.

Q.3.5: In the future there will be better water quality (N P other pollutants).

■ Strongly disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neutral ■ Agree ■ Strongly Agree ■ Not sure

Figure 31: 8 Pie charts representing the agreeableness of the participants to the statements.

The pie charts represented above illustrate a general agreeableness on the impact of climate change being more unfavorable and impactful on agriculture in the future. At the same time, 64% of participants seem to agree that water quality will improve in the future.

The Q3 statements were analyzed together with the various socio-economic factors, as well as the implementation of the measures to find any correlation.

	AgeEXP	Fam	Inc	Edu	FisM	Impl	Q3	MFA
AgeEXP	1.00	0.37	0.01	0.04	0.18	0.06	0.08	0.42
Fam	0.37	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.39
Inc	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.09	0.09	0.30
Edu	0.04	0.05	0.00	1.00	0.04	0.20	0.23	0.58
FisM	0.18	0.08	0.01	0.04	1.00	0.07	0.06	0.35
Impl	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.20	0.07	1.00	0.28	0.58
Q3	0.08	0.05	0.09	0.23	0.06	0.28	1.00	0.65
MFA	0.42	0.39	0.30	0.58	0.35	0.58	0.65	1.00

Legend:

AgeEXP = Age and Experience

Edu = Education level

Q3 = Q3 statements

Fam = Household size

FisM = Farmins is main income

Inc = Income

Impl = Implementation of measure

Table 5: RV coefficients showing the relationship between various socio-economic factors, the implementation of the measures and the opinions of the participants on the Q3 statements.

For Q3 we see a somewhat moderate correlation between the opinions of the statements and the educational level (RV = 0.23) as well as the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.28). There is no correlation between the statements and the age and experience of the participants, nor with household size.

Other factors

In order to find out if any other socio-economical variable has any correlation with the implementation of the measures, an MFA was made using:

Age and experience, municipality, income, land owned, land rented, education, whether farming is or isn't the main income, household size as well as the implementation of all 6 measures combined. Age and experience were included as a single group because of their high correlation.

	AgeEXP	Impl	Mcp	Inc	LandOwn	LandRent	Edu	FisM	Fam	MFA
AgeEXP	1.00	0.06	0.18	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.18	0.37	0.42
Impl	0.06	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.16	0.20	0.07	0.08	0.51
Mcp	0.18	0.09	1.00	0.16	0.10	0.20	0.09	0.23	0.20	0.58
Inc	0.01	0.09	0.16	1.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.30
LandOwn	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.00	1.00	0.01	0.08	0.27	0.00	0.34
LandRent	0.03	0.16	0.20	0.03	0.01	1.00	0.13	0.11	0.02	0.40
Edu	0.04	0.20	0.09	0.00	0.08	0.13	1.00	0.04	0.05	0.52
FisM	0.18	0.07	0.23	0.01	0.27	0.11	0.04	1.00	0.08	0.45
Fam	0.37	0.08	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.08	1.00	0.41
MFA	0.42	0.51	0.58	0.30	0.34	0.40	0.52	0.45	0.41	1.00

Legend:

AgeEXP = Age and experience

Impl = implementaion of all 6 measures

Mcp = municipality

Inc = Income

LandOwn = Land area owned

LandRent = Land area rented

Edu = Edcuation level

FisM = farming is/ins't the main income

Fam = Household size

Table 6: RV coefficients showing the relationship between the socio-economic variables and the implementation of all the measures.

Through the results of the MFA showed in the figure above, we observe a somewhat weak, but still present, correlation between the education of the participants and the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.20) which is higher when combining all the measures compared to individual measures as shown in Table 2. Interestingly, the area of rented land also seems to have a small correlation with the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.16). However, other factors such as age and experience, municipality, or income, do not seem to have any correlation, or at the most a very weak one.

As has been noticed in Table 6, there is some relationship between rented land area and the implementation of the measures. In order to see if there is a particular measure that has the most correlation with the rented land area, an MFA was made as shown in Table 7.

	LandRent	G.S	GW	SCW	RT	BZ	SRP	MFA
LandRent	1.00	0.02	0.23	0.10	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.47
G.S	0.02	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.37
GW	0.23	0.00	1.00	0.29	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.54
SCW	0.10	0.00	0.29	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.10	0.51
RT	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.04	1.00	0.00	0.05	0.40
BZ	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.02	0.36
SRP	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.10	0.05	0.02	1.00	0.41
MFA	0.47	0.37	0.54	0.51	0.40	0.36	0.41	1.00

Legend:

LandRent = Rented land area

SCW = Small constructed wetlands

SRP = Small retention pools in the forest

G.S = Grass and stubble in flood prone areas **RT** = Reduced tillage

GW = Grassed waterways

BZ = Buffer zones

Table 7: RV coefficient showing the relationship between each measures and rented land area.

We can observe above a moderate correlation between GW as well as a small correlation between SCW and the rented land area. As for the other measures no correlation can be observed.

3.4.4 Organizations

Using an MFA, we determined if there was a correlation between information received from various organizations, age, the implementation of the measures as well as the scale of knowledge of each measure. Participants were asked to select which organization has participated in informing them on any of the 6 measures. They had the possibility to choose between NIBIO websites and factsheets, Morsa water district, PURA water district, agricultural office of their respective municipalities, Norsk Landbruksrådgivning (NLR) and Bondelag. Since only one participant had received information from PURA water district, it was removed from the MFA as to not interfere with the results. They were also asked to determine, on a scale of 1 to 5, how much they are knowledgeable on each measure. Figure 32 shows the total number of participants that have received information on any of the 6 measures from the organizations. We notice the agricultural office as being the most common source of information for the

participants concerning natural water retention measures. NLR and Morsa water districts are also common information sources.

Figure 32: Column chart representing the number of participants that received information from the 6 organizations on any of the 6 measures.

Below are group representations, one for each organization, illustrating the correlation between the received information from organizations on any of the measures (Org), the scale of knowledge of each measure (Scale), the implementation of each measure (Impl) as well as the age of the participants (Age).

	Scale	Age	Impl	Org	MFA
Scale	1.00	0.14	0.29	0.08	0.65
Age	0.14	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.47
Impl	0.29	0.04	1.00	0.04	0.70
Org	0.08	0.02	0.04	1.00	0.44
MFA	0.65	0.47	0.70	0.44	1.00

Legend:
Scale = Scale of knowledge of measure
Age = Age of participant
Impl = Implementation of measure
Org = received information from NIBIO

Table 8: RV coefficients showing the relationship between NIBIO (Org) and the scale of knowledge (Scale), age (Age) and the implementation of the measures (Impl).

As illustrated in Table 8, there is an insignificant correlation between received information from NIBIO websites and/or factsheets and the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.04).

In addition, the correlation between the scale of knowledge of the measures and the organization is also very weak ($RV = 0.08$).

	Scale	Age	Impl	Org	MFA
Scale	1.00	0.14	0.29	0.06	0.64
Age	0.14	1.00	0.04	0.03	0.47
Impl	0.29	0.04	1.00	0.03	0.70
Org	0.06	0.03	0.03	1.00	0.43
MFA	0.64	0.47	0.70	0.43	1.00

Legend:
Scale = Scale of knowledge of measure
Age = Age of participant
Impl = Implementation of measure
Org = received information from Morsa water district

Table 9: RV coefficients showing the relationship between Morsa water district (Org) and the scale of knowledge (Scale), age (Age) and the implementation of the measures (Impl).

In the case of Morsa water district (Table 9), we can see a very low correlation between the scale of knowledge of the measure and the organization ($RV = 0.06$) as well as almost no correlation between the organization and the implementation of the measure ($RV = 0.03$).

	Scale	Age	Impl	Org	MFA
Scale	1.00	0.14	0.29	0.09	0.64
Age	0.14	1.00	0.04	0.06	0.48
Impl	0.29	0.04	1.00	0.10	0.71
Org	0.09	0.06	0.10	1.00	0.49
MFA	0.64	0.48	0.71	0.49	1.00

Legend:
Scale = Scale of knowledge of measure
Age = Age of participant
Impl = Implementation of measure
Org = received information from agricultural office

Table 10: RV coefficients showing the relationship between agricultural offices (Org) and the scale of knowledge (Scale), age (Age) and the implementation of the measures (Impl).

We can observe in Table 10 a correlation between the implementation of the measures and receipt of information by the agricultural office of the participants' respective municipalities ($RV = 0.10$), as well as little to no correlation between the scale of knowledge of the measures and the organization ($RV = 0.09$). However, as shown in Figure 32, all the participants except

one has received information from this organization, therefore, having close to no correlation is expected.

	Scale	Age	Impl	Org	MFA
Scale	1.00	0.14	0.29	0.09	0.63
Age	0.14	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.45
Impl	0.29	0.04	1.00	0.19	0.73
Org	0.09	0.02	0.19	1.00	0.51
MFA	0.63	0.45	0.73	0.51	1.00

Legend:
Scale = Scale of knowledge of measure
Age = Age of participant
Impl = Implementation of measure
Org = received information from NLR

Table 11: RV coefficients showing the relationship between NLR (Org) and the scale of knowledge (Scale), age (Age) and the implementation of the measures (Impl).

Table 11 illustrates a weak but present correlation between participants having received information from Norsk Landbruksrådgivning (NLR) and the implementation of the measure (RV = 0.19). In addition, it can also be observed that there is no correlation between age and the organization (RV = 0.02). When observing the scale of knowledge of the measures with the organization, we see a very weak correlation, but slightly higher than the relationship the other organizations have.

	Scale	Age	Impl	Org	MFA
Scale	1.00	0.14	0.29	0.05	0.64
Age	0.14	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.47
Impl	0.29	0.04	1.00	0.08	0.71
Org	0.05	0.02	0.08	1.00	0.45
MFA	0.64	0.47	0.71	0.45	1.00

Legend:
Scale = Scale of knowledge of measure
Age = Age of participant
Impl = Implementation of measure
Org = received information from Bondelag

Table 12: RV coefficients showing the relationship between Bondelag (Org) and the scale of knowledge (Scale), age (Age) and the implementation of the measures (Impl).

Lastly, we can observe in Table 12 a very weak correlation between Bondelag and the implementation of the measures (RV = 0.08), as well as between the scale of knowledge of the measures and the organization (RV = 0.05).

NLR was the only organization to stand out on its correlation with the implementation of the measures. For this reason, we looked into the correlation between NLR and specific measures. Whilst 4/6 measures had no correlation, grassed waterways and small constructed wetlands gave moderate RV coefficients as shown in Table 13.

	NLR		NLR
NLR	1.00	NLR	1.00
ImplGW	0.19	ImplSCW	0.28
ScaleGW	0.04	ScaleSCW	0.06

Legend:
ImplGW = Implementation of grassed waterways
ScaleGW = Scale of knowledge on grassed waterways
ImplSCW = Implementation of small constructed wetlands
ScaleSCW = Scale of knowledge of small constructed wetlands
NLR = Information received from NLR

Table 13: RV coefficients showing the correlation between NLR and the implementation and scale of knowledge of GW and SCW.

In order to see whether there is positive or a negative correlation between NLR and the implementation of the two measures we used an MCA illustrated as a factor map as shown in Figure 33.

NLR_Yes/No = Information received / not received from NLR

SCW_Yes/No = Implementation / non-implementation of small constructed wetlands

GW_Yes/No = Implementation / non-implementation of grassed waterways

Figure 33: Factor map showing the relationship between NLR and the implementation of GW and SCW.

We can conclude from the factor map above that NLR has a positive correlation with the implementation of the measures since SCW_Yes and GW_Yes are closely situated to NLR_Yes and oppositely situated to NLR_No on the first Dimension (Dim1) which represents 53.38% of the variance.

3.4.5 Grants and implementation

Participants were asked whether they received grants from SMIL or RMP while specifying if they were full or partial grants. Using RV coefficients, we can get numerical values for the correlation between 3 groups: Partial grants, full grants and the implementation of the measure Table 14.

	Impl	Full	Part	MFA
Impl	1.00	0.23	0.10	0.58
Full	0.23	1.00	0.37	0.78
Part	0.10	0.37	1.00	0.73
MFA	0.58	0.78	0.73	1.00

Legend:
Impl = Implementation of the measure
Full = Full grants from SMIL/RMP or both
Part = Partial grants from SMIL/RMP or both

Table 14: RV coefficients showing the relationship between full grants, partial grants and the implementation of the measures.

In the figure above we see a correlation between the implementation of the measures and the receipt of full grants, whereas a much weaker relationship between the receipt of partial grants and the implementation of the measures.

4. Discussion

4.1 Online survey program

Although *JotForm* scored high on many aspects that were desired, such as simplicity, esthetics, and large choice of available extensions, it did have disadvantages which might strongly dissuade of its reuse in the future. During the creation of the online survey, the use of conditional logic is critical to make the questionnaire as well adapted to each responder as possible and thus consequently also reducing the completion time. *JotForm* lacked a more clear

and simple way of managing conditional logic for each question. This resulted in some confusion as well as a large amount of time spent on managing the conditional logic in the survey. It was observed during the survey testing phase that Qualtrics survey program had a more simple and clearer way with regard to conditional logic management.

During the data analysis phase, the biggest flaw of *JotForm* was noticed. Although the responses could directly be implemented in an Excel sheet, there was a need for large amount of data pre-processing before being able to analyze. This is due to the way the responses to the survey questions in *JotForm* are transferred to the Excel sheet when the data is exported. Questions having the possibility to select multiple answers were transferred under a single cell in excel. This caused any analysis to believe that each participants' composition of answers for the same question was regarded as one answer, instead of multiple answers. If a responder selected (A), (B), (C) as the answers for a question and another participant selected (A), (C) then these would be considered 2 separate answers instead of two compositions of answers with two common answers for the two participants. This resulted in having to create separate columns in Excel for each possible answer for the same question.

Although *JotForm* was a good choice with regard to the creation of the survey, the program isn't well suited for data management as it doesn't separate answers from multiple answer questions into separate columns, thus making Excel read the selected answers for a single question with multiple possible answers as one. This results in having to heavily pre-process the data before analyzing the results and therefore isn't suited for an analysis of a large dataset. For future survey creation, using another program might be a better option in order to increase manageability of conditional logic as well as lessening the amount of pre-processing of the data prior to the statistical analysis.

4.2 Survey development

The Morsa catchment area is a geographical area that was selected by the Ministry of Climate and Environment for the Water Framework Directive (Morsa, n.d.). For this reason, the local farming community has been subject to several surveys and other forms of participations in the past. Therefore, stakeholder fatigue might already have been quite high, which might have given a disadvantage with regard to the response rate of my questionnaire. Considering the already high stakeholder fatigue, it was important to create a short and simple survey, in order not to lose participation by the responders throughout the survey. 10% response rate might not be a very high response rate, but considering the situation, it could have been much lower if

the survey hadn't been simplified, shortened and adapted to the local conditions. Furthermore, receiving 25 responses in 2 weeks wouldn't have been feasible with a survey based on in-person interviews.

Nonetheless, there might have been confusion among some participants regarding some questions. This may have affected the quality of the information. This is more easily avoided during in-person interviews, as it is possible to further explain any elements that aren't clear to the responder. In addition, online surveys might increase stakeholder fatigue during the participation of the survey in comparison to in-person interviews, as participants aren't guided through the process.

Online surveys may also exclude some participants of a certain age, as computer literacy can affect the will to participate to such surveys. Nonetheless, as mentioned previously in the Materials and Methods chapter, computer literacy is quite high in Norway, and as seen in the results, the average age of responders was 57 years, and there were a couple of participants over the age of 70. According to SSB, the average age of Norwegian farmers has been increasing since the past decades from an average of 48.6 in 2004 to 52.2 in 2020 (Lasse Eika, 2022). The average age of the participants to our survey is somewhat higher than the Norwegian average, therefore it would seem as though age hasn't really excluded participants of older age. It is also important to note that persons having a greater interest, and being more invested in the environment might be the main participants of this survey. Therefore, there is a possibility of a bias that does not fully represent the overall opinions and situation of the local farmer community.

4.3 Measures and benefits

There are two factors that contribute to droughts. Firstly, the increase in temperatures, and secondly, the decrease in precipitation during seasons with high evapotranspiration rates. From 1900 to 2014 the annual mean temperature of mainland Norway has increased by 1°C. The main increase in temperature has been during spring and autumn season, with a statistically insignificant increase in winter (I.Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017). According to the 2017 NCCS report by the Norwegian Environment Agency (Miljødirektoratet), using the RCP8.5 scenario developed by the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC), by the year 2100 temperatures will have risen by an estimated 4.5°C throughout mainland Norway and annual precipitation is projected to increase by 18% (I.Hanssen-Bauer et al., 2017). According to a study (I. Hanssen-Bauer & A.B. Sandø, 2016) there has already been a 27% increase in annual

precipitation since 1900 to 2015 in Østfold, a former county located inside what is Viken County today. The study also predicts a doubling of days with intense rainfall, as well as an increase of the amount of rainfall during these days (I. Hanssen-Bauer & A.B. Sandø, 2016).

High temperatures increase evaporation (European Commission, n.d.-a). Therefore, even if precipitation levels were to remain stable, soil moisture and groundwater levels would still decrease, further enhancing the risk of droughts (Wong et al., 2011). However, periods of low precipitation during the summer have increased in duration. This is most likely due to an increase in temperatures, which causes snow to melt earlier during the season. Early snowmelt decreases the amount of soil water throughout the spring and increases the duration of the summer season (I. Hanssen-Bauer & A.B. Sandø, 2016). The effects of these changes coincide with the responses received from the participants of this study.

All participants mentioned observing droughts the last 10 years, with all except one reporting 2023 as being the last year of an observed drought. In addition, floods and excess water were observed by 17 responders with 16 of them saying the last year observed was in 2023. Figure 34 shows the total rainfall during the year 2023 in Ås, Viken. We can observe a shortage of precipitation during the months of May and June compared to the “normal” (black line) as well as an excess of precipitation during the month of August.

Figure 34: Bar chart showing the total rainfall during each month in Ås, Viken. The blue bars represent the total rainfall and the black lines represents the normal amount of rainfall for each month (YR, 2023).

The increase in drought periods and of intense rainfall has led the Norwegian policy to create measures such as regulations and subsidies, in order to encourage the implementation of practical measures that can reduce the impact of these events. From this study, the most commonly implemented measures in the Morsa catchment are grass and stubble in areas prone to flooding, reduced tillage, and buffer zones. Buffer zones are mandatory in the Morsa catchment area, on areas along streams and lakes. Grass or stubble and reduced tillage are voluntary measures unless situated in exposed watersheds. Grassed waterways, small constructed wetlands and small retention pools in the forest however are all voluntary

measures. This would partly explain why they are less implemented than the three other measures.

When maintaining cover on the soil with organic matter such as with reduced tillage, the decomposition of organic matter enables the creation of voids, improving the porosity of the soil. In addition, fungi and bacteria that decompose the organic matter produce a biochemical that sticks to soil particles and thus improve soil aggregate stability (Rust & Williams, n.d.). If soil aggregates are weak, they risk breaking apart in smaller particles, leading to higher risks of erosion. In addition, low aggregate stability allows the formation of crusts on the surface soil during dry periods, worsening the effects of runoff (Rust & Williams, n.d.). Improved soil porosity enables better water infiltration in the soil. Improved aggregate stability reduces erosion of topsoil. Both these advantages help reduce surface soil runoff, thereby reducing erosion as well reducing water pollution from fertilizers and agrochemicals (Rust & Williams, n.d.).

These advantages greatly coincide with the most common benefits observed by the participants of this study, which are the reduction in soil erosion and the improvement of water quality. In addition, reducing the effects of extreme weather such as floods and droughts have also commonly been mentioned.

4.4 Socio economic factors affecting the implementation of measures

Education

As seen in the results of this study (p. 42, 44 and 46), education has an impact on the opinions of the participants whilst only having a weak impact on the implementation of measures. In addition, we do see education as having a positive impact on the general awareness of the various natural water retention measures. However, although participants were asked to give their level of education, the type of education was not asked. It is therefore not known whether participants have completed a degree in a study-field related to agriculture. According to a report by (Zahl-Thanem et al., 2018), 40% of Norwegian farmers have a high school education related to agriculture, 10% have a higher education (university or college) related to agriculture, and the remaining 50% have an education (high school or higher) non-related to agriculture (Zahl-Thanem et al., 2018). If we apply this to our study, this will mean that 6 people have a background in agriculture and 18 people have a background unrelated to agriculture. However,

because of the close proximity of Morsa catchment to NMBU, the largest agricultural related university in Norway, the percentage of higher education related to agriculture might be higher in this study than what was concluded in the (Zahl-Thanem et al., 2018) study. In addition, Morsa catchment is also situated in the vicinity of NIBIO, which could potentially affect the line of work of the participants, creating a bias in the results of this study.

Several studies have found correlations between the farmers educational level with their adaptation to climate change. Though most of these studies are conducted in third world countries, we do see to a lesser degree some similarities with our case in Norway. In a study (Gebre et al., 2023) conducted in Kenya, a strong positive correlation between the education level of the farmers and their adaptation to measures such as the implementation of drought tolerant crop varieties and crop diversification was observed. In our study, the correlation between the education level and the implementation of the measures is considered weak, contrarily to the study in Kenya.

Climate change has the biggest impact in temperate climates, where most developed countries lie, including Norway (Gagnon-Lebrun & Agrawala, 2006). This means a greater and quicker need for adaptation. Developed countries have the advantage of having more technical and financial resources, enabling more and better information distribution as well as material and financial support to enable farmers to implement measures (Gagnon-Lebrun & Agrawala, 2006). Better information distribution through organizations allows farmers better equal access to information and adaption strategies with any level of education. This could explain the reason education has a lesser impact in our study than it has in the (Gebre et al., 2023) study in Kenya. On the other hand, the study reveals the age of the farmer as being negatively correlated to the implementation of the measures (Gebre et al., 2023).

Age

According to a sociology study on Norwegian farmers (Aasprang, 2012), the youngest as well as the oldest farmers, are the most concerned of the effect of climate change on their farm, as opposed to middle-aged farmers who are less worried. The study further mentions media coverage as a factor impacting the concern for climate change in younger farmers. In the case of older farmers, the study further discusses the possibility of it being caused by witnessing impacts of climate change over a longer time-period. However, older farmers may also be impacted by the passing down of their land. Farmers who don't have younger family members

that will take over the farm are less concerned of the impact of climate change on their farm in the coming years (Aasprang, 2012).

In our study, experience and age do not seem to be directly correlated with the implementation of the measures (p.47). However, it does seem to affect opinions on the practical benefits of certain measures, notably the protection of watercourses (Table 3), which in turn, might affect their decision to implement measures. Therefore, there might be an indirect correlation between age and experience and the implementation of various measures.

In addition to better information distribution, financial and technical support, a greater international base has allowed develop countries better adaptation planning (Gagnon-Lebrun & Agrawala, 2006). The OPTAIN project itself is a project funded by the EU, also including outside members such as Norway and Switzerland. This has allowed developed countries to develop strategies and implement measures at a quicker pace and with greater means than it has in third world countries. This could explain the reason as to why age and experience doesn't have the same impact in Norway as it has in the study from Kenya. Older generations in Norway have already been implementing some of the measures for some decades. As some participants commented in the survey, measures such as grass or stubble have been implemented since the early 1970s. Others mention for the same measure that it was required by the county governor in the 90s. One participant mentioned implementing grassed waterways for 35 years. These examples indicate an adaptation to climate change in agriculture that has started already decades ago in Norway, therefore, even though the average age of the farmers in Norway is higher than in Kenya, age does not have the same effect on the implementation of these measures.

Resource availability

Many of the participants that were asked why they haven't implemented certain measures said they didn't see the need with a few mentioning financial reasons. Some measures that aren't implemented are also due to the production of the farmers. In the context of reduced tillage for example, both participants having not reduced tillage have livestock as their main production. However, this excludes participants who haven't heard about the measure and thus count as most of the reasons why most measures were not implemented. Therefore, lack of information on the measure seems to be the main reason as to why certain measures are not in place.

Grants from SMIL and RMP seem to have significantly affected the implementation of measures. Simultaneously, income has been observed as having no correlation with the

implementation. It can therefore be concluded that the availability of subsidies in Norway enable the implementation of measures without having it negatively impact their income.

Land area

Through the results of this study, we have seen that the size of owned land area has no correlation with the implementation of measures and that, on the contrary, size of rented land is correlated to the implementation of measures, more specifically, grassed waterways.

A study (Skaalsveen et al., 2022) reveals that farmers who are renting out land around Akersvannet (Norway) were more concerned on keeping the water quality of downstream water high. The reason mentioned by the study is that low water quality could negatively impact the price of the rented land, thus the efforts to maintain a high water-quality. This could explain the correlation found in this study between the area of rented land and the use of measures, more specifically grassed waterways.

Low value variables

Some variables were unused during the analysis, such as gender, and the participant's position in the farm. Out of the 25 participants only 2 people were not farm owners or co-owners. Also, only 1 participant was female. Therefore, since this data would have no value in the analysis, it was ignored.

4.5 Organizations

Farmers implement measures based on the quality of information received, on legal guidelines, as well as on the availability of subsidies. By looking at the correlation between the implementation of measures and the information received from various organizations, we found NLR to be the only organization having any correlation. However, it is important to note that another organization, the agricultural office, was selected by all except one farmer as being the source of information on one or more of the measures. This results in the MFA not finding its role correlated with the implementation of measures, even though it was the most common source of information for the participants on the measures.

In order to understand the reason NLR is correlated with the implementation of measures, it is important to understand the role these organizations have. Research and projects led by research centers such as NIBIO, develop solutions and measures for the agricultural sector. NLR and the agricultural office provides farmers with logistical, financial or legal information

on the implementation of measures. NLR and the agricultural office are either part or very familiar with the agricultural sector, which creates trust among the farmers. In addition, farmers can request subsidies directly from the agricultural office (Blankenberg, 2023).

5. Conclusion

Through this study it can be concluded that there are several factors that affect the farmer's decision to implement natural water retention measures in the Morsa catchment area.

Education level has shown to positively affect the general knowledge of NWRMs as well as having a slight direct influence on their implementation. It also impacts opinions on climate change adaptation which affect decision-making regarding the implementation of various measures. Complementing this, age and experience does not directly correlate with the implementation of measures but does affect opinions on the practical benefits of certain measures, thus indirectly affecting the decision to implement certain measures. Trust between the source of information on the NWRMs and the farmer as well as access to subsidies, are also important factors that impact the decision to implement measures. In addition, maintaining a high land value in order to rent out land at better prices seem to be a motivator for the maintaining of high soil and water quality through the implementation of water retention measures. The most limiting factor, however, seems to be the lack of knowledge, as most measures that weren't implemented were reported as not being known by the participants.

Grass or stubble in areas prone to flooding, reduced tillage as well as the use of buffer zones have been observed as being the most common practices among farmers in the Morsa catchment, probably due to them being mandatory in particular conditions. Benefits of the measures have been reported by the participants, as having mainly reduced soil erosion, improved water quality, and protected their land from extreme weather events.

This study included 25 participants, from which some conclusions can be made. However, a study on a larger scale, for example on the whole county, would give a higher statistical value to the analysis. A larger scale study could potentially adjust correlations that were found in this study and maybe identify other relationships. A study on a larger area would also potentially involve participants with more diverse backgrounds and lines of work, which could potentially reduce bias.

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